

Ischemic Heart Disease Prediction Using Machine Learning and Explainable AI

Mohaiminul Kabir¹, Mohammed Jieaf¹, Jawad Al Mujahid², Sakib Rahman¹, Ekramul Hasib¹, Md.Mortuza Ahmmed³

¹Department of Computer Science, American International University Bangladesh

²Department of Computer Science, International Islamic University Chittagong

³Department of Mathematics, American International University Bangladesh

Abstract— Ischaemic heart disease (IHD) is one of the common causes of death worldwide and early prediction is important for appropriate treatment. In this work we applied machine learning models for prediction of ischemic heart disease. The models are Random Forest, XGBoost, LightGBM and gradient boosting. The Random Forest model has the best performance with an accuracy of 92.60 and AUC of 94.62 after pre-processing and model evaluation. The explainability analysis by ELI5 also showed that age was the most important risk factor.

Keywords— Ischemic Heart Disease (IHD), Machine Learning, Random Forest, Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI)

I. Introduction

Ischemic heart disease (IHD) is one of the major health issues worldwide due to the inadequate blood supply to the heart through blockages of the coronary arteries that lead to life-threatening conditions such as heart attacks. This study describes the development of a machine learning model to predict IHD using large clinical and demographic datasets and the application of Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) techniques to identify the main risk factors and to improve the model's interpretability.

II. Methodology

In this study, machine learning was used to predict ischemic heart disease. Kaggle was initially used to download the dataset that contains clinical and demographic data on risk factors for ischemic heart disease.

Pre-processing: The missing values were managed during the data pre-processing as follows: Missing numerical values were imputed with the mean and missing categorical values with the mode. No duplicates were detected. Outliers were treated with the capping method to reduce their impact on the performance of the model.

Model Evaluation: After preprocessing, the dataset was split into training and testing sets. SMOTE method was applied to control the class imbalance of the target variable. Several machine learning algorithms were trained, tested for the prediction of ischemic heart disease. Model performance was evaluated based on accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, AUC and K-fold cross validation for reliability.

Explainable AI: The model was interpreted using Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) techniques, particularly ELI5, to the important features to predict ischemic heart disease.

III. Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents **Random Forest (RF)** classifier showed better performance than the other models in the prediction of ischemic heart disease, with an accuracy of **92.60%**, precision of **92.44%**, recall of **92.60%**, F1-score of **92.54%**, and AUC of **94.62%**. The performance of **XGBoost (XGB)**, **LightGBM (LGBM)**,

Table 1. Performance Comparison of ML Models

Model	Acc.	Prec.	Rec.	F1	AUC
RF	92.60	92.44	92.60	92.54	94.62
XGB	89.45	89.31	89.45	89.37	92.91
LGBM	87.01	87.05	87.01	87.81	89.06
GB	85.90	85.33	85.90	85.48	88.93

and **Gradient Boosting (GB)** was comparatively lower.

Figure 1. Confusion Matrix and Eli5 Analysis

The **Random Forest** model was good at classifying the cases of ischemic heart disease. The true negatives and true positives values are high but there are some misclassifications. Feature importance analysis indicated that the most important predictor was **Age** followed by **Age²**, **Race/Ethnicity**, **Calcium Intake**, **Body Weight**, and **Gender**, demonstrating the model's capability in finding important risk factors.

IV. Conclusion

The current study showed the effectiveness of machine learning techniques for prediction of ischemic heart disease. Of the models considered, the random forest classifier was the best performing model for prediction. The results also emphasized the importance of the key risk factors in predicting the disease, particularly age. Thus, the proposed approach can help in early diagnosis and better decision making in health care systems.

References

- [1] N. Khalid, S. C. Higgins, M. Abdullah, H. Munshi, M. Hasnat, R. Doshi, P. Michael, R. Vasudev, S. E. Fayeze, and

J. A. Panza, "Ischemic heart disease-related mortality trends in the United States and prediction using machine learning," *Annals of Medicine and Surgery*, vol. 87, no. 7, pp. 4145–4151, 2025.